

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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"THE HAND THAT HOLDS THE KEY"

On this sacred stage, I take my stand,
No crown I wear, no staff I command,
But armed with lessons, pure and true,
I mold both spirit and the mind anew.
I sow in beings the roots of grace,
That knowledge binds through time and space.

Though not for gain my tireless hours are spent,
Delight is drawn, a sacred instrument.
The thought once kindled, gleams and glows
A beacon bright that ever grows.
Through my labor, they come to find,
And walk the path that shapes the mind.

Hence yearn, O noble dreamer, be wise,
Seek the gateway where truth lies.
Unseal thine path ere it's too late,
Toward the realm of the divine gate.
For whoever gains wisdom's excess,
Though meager in gold, shall find success.